

EDITORIAL

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Emerging Challenges of E-Waste Management: Serious Threats to Environmental Safety

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Abstract

Electronic waste (e-waste) has become a major environmental issue due to its hazardous contents, such as toxic substances like Mercury, Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs), and Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs), which pose significant risks to human health and ecosystems. The rapid pace of technological advancement and the increasing consumption of electronic devices have caused a substantial surge in e-waste generation. In 2019, global e-waste production reached 53.6 million metric tons, with projections suggesting it will double by 2050. High-income countries have made strides in developing policies and infrastructure for e-waste recycling; however, a significant portion of this waste is exported to low-income countries, where improper processing methods lead to serious environmental and health hazards. Although recycling e-waste has substantial economic value, with raw material recovery potentially worth \$57 billion, only 17.4% of global e-waste was properly recycled in 2019, emphasizing the urgent need for improved management strategies and international cooperation to address this growing issue.

Keywords: E-waste; Management; Threat; Environment; Safety**Introduction**

The global community faces a range of environmental challenges, many exacerbated by industrial activities (Tayal et al., 2023; Singh, 2022; Pandiarajan et al., 2023; Mehra and Chadha, 2023; Hassan, 2023). Among these, electronic waste (e-waste) has emerged as a critical concern due to the toxic and hazardous substances it contains, posing severe risks to both human health and ecosystems (Mahajan, 2023). Rapid technological advancements, coupled with the increasing consumption of electronic devices, have significantly escalated the production of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), commonly referred to as e-waste. E-waste consists of both valuable materials, such as rare earth metals, and hazardous elements, including Mercury, Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs), and Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), as well as more recently introduced toxic pollutants like Organophosphate Esters (OPEs) (Chen and Wei, 2020). Despite the economic potential of recycling e-waste, which is valued at around \$57 billion USD, high-income nations still face challenges in effectively managing their e-waste, as large amounts are exported to low-income countries for processing under suboptimal conditions (Johnson and Balasubramanian, 2021). In many developing countries, the regulatory frameworks for e-waste management remain inadequate, and public awareness is insufficient, leading to significant environmental and health risks. In 2019, the global per capita generation of e-waste was 7.3 kg, with total global e-waste reaching 53.6 million metric tons, a 21% increase from 2015 levels. The total amount is projected to increase to 120 million metric tons by 2050 (Global E-Waste Statistics Partnership, 2020). As economic development accelerates, the demand for electronic devices continues to drive e-waste production. However, despite these growing concerns, only 17.4% of global e-waste was properly recycled in 2019, with the remainder being exported to low-income nations where unsafe processing practices contribute to severe environmental degradation (Sinha and Jha, 2019).

The definition of electronic waste (e-waste) varies across different countries, but the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) recognizes WEEE as the fastest-growing waste category globally (UNEP, 2018). E-waste includes both hazardous and non-hazardous components and consists of discarded or unwanted electronic devices that are no longer in use. As technological advancements

progress and the lifespan of electronic products shortens, e-waste has emerged as a critical environmental issue, second only to plastic pollution. E-waste encompasses a broad range of devices, from large household appliances like microwaves, ovens, and washing machines, to information and communication technologies such as computers, mobile phones, and televisions. Increasingly, electronic products are also integrated into green technologies, such as solar panels and electric vehicles, adding another layer of complexity to their environmental impact. The composition of e-waste varies depending on the type of equipment, with communication electronics containing more heavy metals and precious materials, while household appliances consist mainly of plastics and metals (Kumar and Singh, 2022). The United Nations University (UNU) has categorized Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE) into six distinct groups to better understand the various components and challenges associated with e-waste (Global E-Waste Statistics Partnership, 2020).

Global occurrence of e-waste

E-waste contamination is particularly widespread in regions like China, India, Pakistan, and several African nations. In China, areas such as Guangdong, Zhejiang, and Tianjin provinces have seen significant e-waste contamination, with heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Copper (Cu), Mercury (Hg), Zinc (Zn), Chromium (Cr), and Nickel (Ni), as well as toxic chemicals like Polybrominated Diphenyl Ethers (PBDEs) and Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs) found at elevated concentrations (Chen and Wei, 2020). Despite a 2010 ban on small private workshops in China to reduce hazardous e-waste dismantling practices, informal recycling continues in areas such as Guiyu and Baihe village, where contamination remains a major concern (Sinha and Jha, 2019). In India, the third-largest e-waste generator globally, approximately 95% of e-waste is processed using rudimentary methods, including landfilling, which contributes to significant environmental pollution (Sinha and Jha, 2019). Studies from cities such as New Delhi, Kolkata, and Mumbai have reported elevated levels of heavy metals and toxic chemicals in soils surrounding e-waste processing sites (Johnson and Balasubramanian, 2021). Similarly, in Pakistan, cities like Lahore and Karachi have shown elevated concentrations of metals and other pollutants in surface soils, resulting from unsafe recycling practices (Kumar and Singh, 2022). Reports from other countries in Southeast Asia, including the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam, have also documented significant contamination from e-waste recycling activities. In Africa, countries like Cameroon, Ghana, and Nigeria have reported soil pollution from e-waste processing, with heavy metals like Lead (Pb), Zinc (Zn), and Chromium (Cr) detected at high concentrations. Oceania, particularly in Australia, has reported contamination with toxic chemicals such as PBDEs and Brominated Flame Retardants in e-waste recycling areas (Wright and Schulz, 2021). These regions face considerable challenges in managing e-waste due to the prevalence of informal recycling practices and the lack of effective regulations and infrastructure (Sinha and Jha, 2019).

Table 1. Various studies related to the e-waste production in different countries

Reference	Summary	Findings	Outcomes
E-waste: application ethics towards reutilizations (2023)	In 2020, global e-waste production was expected to exceed 50 million tonnes, with India contributing an estimated annual output of 2 million tonnes, making it one of the top five e-waste-producing countries worldwide.	E-waste is a rapidly growing global waste stream. Informal sector processes over 90% of India's e-waste.	Informal sector dominates e-waste management in India; Unscientific e-waste disposal activities have negative environmental and health consequences.
Ferreira et al. (2024)	E-waste production is estimated at 20-50 million tons annually, with only 20-25% undergoing formal recycling. This highlights the urgent need for advanced analytical methods to address the environmental impact of electronic waste proliferation.	Robust models for Al, Cu, and Fe quantification developed. Challenges in quantifying aluminum in e-waste samples identified.	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) and X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) techniques used for analysis; Multivariate calibration strategies employed for calibration
Yken et al. (2021)	In 2019, global e-waste production reached 53.6 million tons, projected to increase to 74.7 million tons by 2030. This rise is driven by higher consumption rates, shorter life cycles.	E-waste production reached 53.6 million tons in 2019. Only 17.4% of e-waste was recycled globally in 2019.	Global e-waste production and recycling technologies were studied; Discussion of barriers and enablers for e-waste recycling.

Ghimire et al. (2020)	In 2019, global e-waste production reached 53.6 million metric tons, with China contributing approximately 19% and the United States as the second largest producer. Only 14 countries accounted for over 65% of total e-waste generation that year.	E-waste production exceeds human population growth rate. Only 17.4% of e-waste is recycled properly.	Integration of existing data on production rates Exploration of tangible solutions for e-waste management
Sonawane et al. (2023)	In 2019, an estimated 53 million metric tons of e-waste were produced, with projections reaching 74.7 million metric tons by 2030. The raw material value of e-waste was approximately \$57 billion.	E-waste recycling releases hazardous chemicals affecting health. Developing countries lack resources to assess toxic exposure.	Analytical data for chemical exposure assessment; Approaches to minimize risks and raise awareness.
Ujjaival et al. (2023)	In 2019, India generated an estimated 0.77 to 3.2 million tonnes of e-waste, with 164,663 tonnes dismantled and recycled. Globally, 53.6 million tonnes of e-waste were produced, projected to rise to 74.7 million tonnes by 2030.	E-waste management in India faces significant challenges. Informal recycling practices lead to negative environmental impacts.	Mechanical separation; Pyro-metallurgy; Hydrometallurgy studies
Cornelis et al. (2017)	In 2016, global e-waste production reached 44.7 million metric tonnes, averaging 6.1 kg per inhabitant. This figure is projected to rise to 52.2 million metric tonnes, or 6.8 kg per inhabitant, by 2021.	Global e-waste reached 44.7 million metric tonnes in 2016. Expected increase to 52.2 million metric tonnes by 2021.	Statistical analysis based on global e-waste generation data; Comparison of e-waste quantities between 2014 and 2016.
Kaushik (2018)	Worldwide, E-waste production is estimated at 20 to 50 million tonnes per annum. In India, the situation is exacerbated by both domestically produced E-waste and that discarded by developed countries, highlighting the urgent need for effective management strategies.	E-waste contains hazardous substances affecting health and environment. Poor management in India exacerbates the e-waste problem.	Donating used electronic items for reuse; Separating and selling or donating e-waste to organizations
Bagwan (2023)	The study predicts that from 2023 to 2030, the average E-waste generated in Maharashtra will be 163,563.15 MT, with forecasted values increasing steadily, reaching 248 recyclers by 2030, indicating significant growth in E-waste production.	Average E-waste generation predicted at 163563.15 MT by 2030. E-waste recyclers expected to increase by 7.23% annually.	ARIMA models for time series analysis and forecasting; Analysis of E-waste processing capacity trends.
Kumar et al. (2017)	In 2014, global e-waste production reached approximately 41 million tonnes, increasing at a rate of 3–5% annually. The study highlights a direct correlation between a country's GDP and its e-waste generation, while population impact is minimal.	E-waste reached 41 million tonnes in 2014. GDP correlates with e-waste production, not population.	Overview of global e-waste generation and sales; Importance and benefits of recycling emphasized

Possible adverse effects of heavy metals, PCBs, PBDEs and PAHs

The presence of heavy metals in soil due to e-waste processing can cause significant ecological and health concerns. Elevated concentrations of metals like Copper (Cu), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni), and Zinc (Zn) have been shown to induce mutations in living cells, potentially leading to carcinogenic effects. These metals can increase soil acidity, making it unsuitable for agriculture and affecting plant growth. For example, Copper can induce leaf chlorosis and retard plant growth, while Lead exposure can disrupt photosynthesis and plant morphology.

Cadmium exposure can alter plant enzyme functions and stunt root and shoot growth. Furthermore, heavy metals can bioaccumulate through the food chain, posing severe risks to human and animal health, particularly for children, who are more vulnerable due to increased soil contact. Epidemiological studies suggest that long-term exposure to metals like Lead, Nickel, and Cadmium can have carcinogenic effects, while Chromium exposure may lead to chromosomal aberrations and mutations (Kumar and Singh, 2022).

Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs) are another class of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) that bioaccumulate in the food chain due to their long half-lives and lipophilic nature. High concentrations of PCBs in the environment have been linked to reproductive toxicity, birth defects, and disruption of cellular processes. Non-ortho PCBs, which have a planar structure, are particularly toxic and carcinogenic. Their release during e-waste recycling, especially when electronic components are burned, poses significant health risks to workers and nearby communities. The risk of PCB exposure is compounded in areas where informal e-waste processing is prevalent, as regulatory oversight is limited (Johnson and Balasubramanian, 2021).

Polybrominated Diphenyl Ethers (PBDEs) are persistent environmental contaminants that tend to bind strongly to soil and sediment particles, remaining in the environment for extended periods. These chemicals can disrupt microbial communities and harm living organisms. While the toxicity of BDE-209, the most common PBDE, is still under study, it has been shown that higher-brominated PBDEs can degrade into more bioavailable lower-brominated forms, which are more likely to affect plants. For example, rice plants have been shown to absorb these chemicals (Wright and Schulz, 2021). Humans can be exposed to PBDEs through the ingestion of contaminated soil or food or via dermal contact, and the persistence and bioaccumulation of PBDEs make them a significant environmental and health concern.

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) are hydrophobic compounds that tend to adhere to soil particles and can be transported over long distances. Their mobility in soil depends on factors like moisture content, pH, and soil texture. In dry soils, PAHs can volatilize into the air. Higher molecular weight PAHs are more strongly adsorbed to soil particles, affecting their bioavailability and mobility. The persistence of PAHs in soil can disrupt microbial populations and hinder bacterial activity, negatively impacting soil health and fertility. The presence of PAHs in e-waste processing areas further contributes to soil contamination, with potential risks to human health and the environment (Sinha and Jha, 2019).

Health Risks and Toxicity

The health risks associated with e-waste recycling are numerous and often involve the direct exposure of workers to hazardous substances like heavy metals, flame retardants, and persistent organic pollutants (POPs). In informal e-waste recycling operations, workers are exposed to harmful chemicals through inhalation, skin contact, and ingestion. Workers handling e-waste in open-air environments, often without protective gear, may inhale toxic fumes from burning plastics or suffer skin contact with hazardous chemicals. Long-term exposure to these toxins can result in respiratory diseases, neurological disorders, and developmental issues, especially among children (Kumar and Singh, 2022). The adverse health effects are particularly concerning in countries where informal recycling practices are widespread and regulatory frameworks are inadequate.

Conclusion

The improper management of e-waste continues to present significant environmental and health challenges worldwide. Despite advances in technology and regulatory measures in high-income nations, the export of e-waste to developing countries and the persistence of informal recycling practices exacerbate the global e-waste crisis. The associated risks, particularly from heavy metals, PBDEs, PAHs, and PCBs, threaten ecosystems, soil fertility, and public health. Addressing the e-waste issue requires a multifaceted approach, including stricter regulations, better public awareness, and the development of sustainable recycling technologies. International cooperation and the promotion of environmentally friendly recycling methods, such as urban mining and green chemistry, are essential to mitigate the negative impact of e-waste and recover valuable resources for future use.

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